

Improving Zero-Shot Template-Based 6D Pose Estimation with Geometric Features

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Abstract. 6D Object Pose Estimation is a fundamental problem in robotics and augmented reality. Most of today’s state-of-the-art approaches rely on deep learning and require large sets of training images depicting the target objects. A growing number of algorithms try to generalize from a set of known objects, available for training, to unseen objects at test time. Among those, GigaPose is a template-based approach, that renders the target object in an onboarding phase shortly before inference and uses learned latent codes of these renderings and observed objects for feature matching. While learned representation prove powerful in a wide range of tasks, we propose the integration of additional purely geometric features, which can be extracted basically for free from the available 3D meshes during the onboarding phase. This representation is then used as an additional input for template- and 2D-2D correspondence matching in our approach. We consider multiple relevant features and, implementing one of them, demonstrate improved performance on the core datasets of the relevant BOP Challenge. Our results suggest that, indeed, utilizing additional geometric features can improve the relevant metrics without much additional cost.

Keywords: Computer Vision · Machine Learning · Object Pose Estimation.

1 Introduction

6D object pose estimation (6DOPE) is a crucial task in computer vision that involves determining the position and orientation $T \in SE(3)$ of objects in 3D space. 6DOPE is a relevant task for various fields, including robotics, augmented reality (AR), and quality insurance systems. In robotics, robots can better understand and interact with their environment, enabling them to perform complex tasks such as object grasping, solving assembly tasks, and navigating in cluttered environments. In augmented reality applications, determining the pose of objects in relation to the camera system allows for seamless integration of digital content into the physical environment. AR is widely used in interactive gaming, industrial design, and architectural visualization. Quality insurance systems allow for

(semi-)automatic inspection of objects, detecting faulty objects and relevant defects, as is e.g. done in the ZDZW-project (<https://www.zdzw-project.eu>). State-of-the-art pose estimators such as GDRN-Net [45] and GDNRPP [23] perform well by overfitting to known objects, i.e. the target objects need to be available during training. Often these networks are trained on physically-based renderings attained by rendering the (required) 3D meshes. However, there is a problem with this approach: Once new objects become available and part of the target set, the network needs to be trained again. A new group of algorithms explicitly try to estimate the pose of unseen objects. The BOP Challenge [42], a leading benchmark for 6DOPE, introduced the task of unseen object localication, in its last year’s installment [18]. The second best approach MegaPose [20] received an improved version since, called GigaPose [27]. GigaPose extracts learned features from object observations and templates, rendered from (required) 3D meshes, and finds correspondences by matching them based on similarity. We propose to extend this matching phase by incorporating additional features that are readily available via 3D mesh extraction. These features help to guide the matching process and, in our tests on the 7 Core BOP datasets, lead to improved pose estimation performance following three relevant metrics.

In summary, the contributions of our work are:

- We propose a framework to extend the template-based pose estimator GigaPose with geometric features.
- We discuss potentially interesting geometric features and select the most promising to evaluate the viability of our approach.
- We implement our extension and outperform the original algorithm on the BOP core datasets.

2 Related Work

This chapter is structured into 3 parts giving an overview over the relevant related work. We start with foundation models and large-scale pre-trained models, which are often used for initial feature extraction. Furthermore, we summarize current *model-free* and *model-based* few-shot and zero-shot methods for generalizable 6D pose estimation. Finally, we look into applicable geometric features to support 6DOPE.

2.1 Foundation and large-scale pre-trained models

Large-scale pre-training and especially self-supervised pre-training of deep learning models, such as in vision transformer [29] and diffusion model [51] architectures, can be used to learn to extract strong features from given inputs.

Vision-transformer-based models [2, 29] and [8] present vision transformers that enable the extraction of general-purpose visual features, without requiring

fine-tuning to work across different tasks. DINOv2 is often used to measure the similarity of image-contents, making it a useful for pose estimation methods [10, 27, 47]. SAM [19] and the follow-up FastSAM [54] utilizing the light-weight CNN YOLOv8 [36], are foundation models for zero-shot semantic segmentation, that can be used to propose segmentations for 6DOPE [28]. Depth Anything [49] incorporates a DINOv2-Encoder and a DPT-Decoder [34] to perform zero-shot monocular depth estimation. CNOS(FastSam) [28], a two-step zero-shot method for semantic segmentation of unseen objects, was chosen as a prior and baseline for several tasks in the BOP Challenge.

Diffusion-model-based An alternative to Vision-transformers are diffusion models. The authors of [51] argue that features extracted from Stable Diffusion [37] can be used to learn multiple properties like scene geometry, shadows and depth, but are less accurate in cluttered scenes and exhibit a slower inference time. The methods proposed in [52] and its successor [53] extract semantic features for zero-shot semantic correspondence estimation from 2 parallel backbones (DINOv2 and Stable Diffusion) and fuse their outputs to obtain more expressive features to establish 2D-2D correspondences between 2 images. DIFT [43] is another promising method to establish 2D-2D correspondences between two images for semantic, geometric, and temporal correspondence extraction. Diffusion Hyperfeatures [25] extracts feature-representations from different layers at different time-steps of the diffusion process and then aggregates them with a special aggregation network. Features for real images are obtained from the inversion process and semantic correspondence matching is done with a nearest neighbour search.

2.2 Generalizable 6D Pose Estimation

Generalizable pose estimation methods are methods that try to generalize to objects that were not seen during training. Instance-level methods [7, 17, 22, 32, 40] can only generalize to the objects that were seen during training. Category-level methods [6, 21, 46, 48] are able to generalize inside a learned category representation, but suffer outside of it. Generalizable 6DOPE seeks to mitigate the problems of both instance- and category-specific approaches and can be divided in the two major categories of model-based and model-free methods.

Model-based Model-based methods seek to exploit information from high quality 3D models of unseen objects, to generalize to instances of the corresponding object. These methods tend to be in the zero-shot category. MegaPose [20] is a render-and-compare based zero-shot approach for 6DOPE, that only requires a 3D model and object of interest annotations. A large-scale synthetic training dataset was generated to facilitate the generalization to unseen objects. ZeroPose [4] is a zero-shot 6D pose estimation pipeline containing a zero-shot instance-segmentor, utilizing SAM and ImageBind [12], and a zero-shot pose estimation

part based on 3D-3D correspondences from depth / pointcloud. ZS6D [1] employs CNOS for zero-shot instance-detection and segmentation, which is used to extract dense visual descriptors with DINO[2]. PnP [26] and RANSAC [11] are then used to estimate a pose. FoundPose [30] uses 3D object meshes in an onboarding-phase and a RGB image in conjunction with a DINOv2-based bag-of-words approach for 6DOPE. This representation is then used to establish 2D-3D correspondences to obtain pose hypotheses that are in the end optimized by feature metric refinement. GigaPose [27] is a CAD-based novel-object 6DOPE method that only uses RGB inputs and is based on MegaPose [20] and uses a coarse pose estimation part and a pose refiner part. A fine-tuned DINOv2 [29] trained on *ShapeNet* [3] and *Google scanned objects (GSO)*[9] is used for matching and 2D-2D correspondences between an image and template are utilized to estimate the remaining 4 degrees of freedom.

Model-free Model-free methods circumvent the requirement of 3D models by utilizing other types of annotations to infer the pose of an unseen object. FS6D [16] is a few-shot 6DOPE approach which can generalize to an unseen object by providing a few support views without training, leveraging RGB and depth data, a pre-trained transformer (*ShapeNet*[3]) and the Umeyama algorithm (Kabsch)[44] to match an object from multiple views. Gen6D [24] uses posed support images for accurate pose estimation, via an object detector, a viewpoint selector and a pose-refiner. OnePose++ [15] is a structure from motion (SfM) based approach, that works on a sequence containing the object of interest, using the detector-free matching method LOFTR [41] and a 2D-3D matching network to establish correspondences between the image and the reconstructed model. POPE [10], short for *Promptable Object Pose Estimation*, is a zero-shot approach for detecting any object in any scene. It uses large-scale pre-trained foundation models like DINOv2 and SAM to obtain the top-k feature proposal correspondences between segment and query image, which can be used to compute the relative pose between the query image (prompt) and the target object in new views. Cas6D [31] tackles 6DOPE with a cascading framework, that only uses a target view image and support view images with pose annotations, utilizing a correlation approach based on VGG and DINO features. A similarity network is used to obtain the top-k support images and their pose annotation. These are utilized in a feature pyramid cascading refiner narrowing down the pose estimation until the best estimate is found.

2.3 Geometry Features

The usage of intermediate geometry representations has been shown to facilitate 6DOPE [7, 17, 40, 45], helping to alleviate ambiguities in purely visual representations of objects. GDR-Net [45] takes RGB images for input and computes multiple intermediate geometric features like dense 2D-3D correspondences and surface region attention. These intermediate geometric features are then used in the differentiable Patch-PnP algorithm to regress the pose. The follow-up

GDRNPP [23] was improved in several ways, utilizing more domain randomization, a better backbone, and predicting an additional mask during training. SO-Pose [7] is a GDR-Net based approach for 6DOPE that tries to solve the problem of self-occlusion by utilizing a two-layer representation of a 3D object. HybridPose [40] uses a hybrid intermediate representation to express different geometric information in a given RGB input image. HybridPose predicts key-points, edge-vectors and symmetry correspondences, which are then fed into a pose regressor that uses the 3 intermediate representation to obtain the best fitting pose for aligning the intermediate 2D and 3D representations. CorNet [33] is a specialized method for estimating 6D poses of objects from their corners, which are found by a Faster-RCNN. A RANSAC-like algorithm detects and estimates the object’s 3D pose by matching the 3D corners to the ones detected in an input image. EPOS [17] predicts a 6D pose using a 3D model and an RGB input. An encoder-decoder is utilized to predict correspondences between pixels in an RGB image and surface fragments on the corresponding 3D model. Pixels of an object can be mapped to multiple fragments, which allows the incorporation of object symmetries.

3 Methodology

First, we introduce a selection of relevant geometric features, which are readily available through 3D object meshes. We discuss these features and select the most promising for testing our hypothesis. Finally, we explain our extension of GigaPose in detail, introducing a small additional network for feature prediction.

Fig. 1: Selection of geometric features considered to extend GigaPose. From top left to bottom right: masked original image, extracted edge points, harris key points, normal maps at 64 points sampled using fps, normal maps at 256 points sampled using fps, depth image.

Figure 1 shows a number of relevant geometric features, which are motivated and described in this section.

Edge Key Points. As a first geometric feature we consider the usage of the *discrete mean curvature measure* as discussed in [5]. The feature corresponds to the mean curvature of a sphere centered on a point. Computed for all points, we select the 50th percentile of points. Our intuition for the usefulness of edge key points lies in the high descriptiveness of the curvature for surfaces.

Normals at FPS Points. Farthest Point Sampling (FPS) is a technique to select a subset of points from a larger set based on their distance from each other. The goal of FPS is to choose points that are as far apart from each other as possible while still effectively representing the overall structure or characteristics of the data. The number of points to be sampled can be adjusted, resulting in either a sparser or denser representation of the object. We think FPS might be useful for its inherent property of sampling evenly spread out points. But instead of predicting only the points, we consider to include surface information. Therefore, we suggest to predict the normal maps at the key point locations.

3D Harris Key Points. Harris corner and edge detection is a well established 2D algorithm [13]. [39] propose a point of interest detector for 3D objects, which utilizes the Harris operator. Their method employs an adaptive approach to determine the neighborhood of a vertex, enabling accurate calculation of the Harris response and proves to be robust against various transformations. We think 3D Harris key points encode significant geometric properties and should be helpful to learn a meaningful latent representation.

Depth. As suggested by the GigaPose authors, depth is an intuitively meaningful feature. Measuring the per-pixel distance of an object directly encodes the visible surface. With the emergence of powerful depth estimation algorithms [35, 50], incorporating depth also becomes increasingly feasible.

Discussion Among the listed feature candidates, we observe significant differences during our evaluation, as shown in Figure 1. For example, we prefer the sparse nature of key points over the continuous signal of depth estimates because a small number of key points can already encode a meaningful object representation. However, we also require an even distribution of features across the object surface, which is often lacking with Harris key points, as they are unevenly distributed and low in number. FPS key points are evenly distributed by design, but their geometric significance is somewhat reduced compared to corners and edges. On the other hand, edge key points are sparse, inherently meaningful, and well-distributed across the object surface, clustering around geometrically significant details such as edges and corners. Therefore, we proceed to test our hypothesis—that geometric features improve GigaPose’s template matching—by incorporating edge key points.

3.1 Extending GigaPose

We propose to extend the first of the two steps defined in GigaPose, namely the DINOv2-based template-matching to determine out-of-plane rotation. In

Fig. 2: Overview of our geometric feature network (GeoNet). The encoder is trained without geometry features and afterwards frozen. We introduce an additional mapping layer to transform $v \in V$ to $w \in W$, which are used as input for our decoder head. The decoder head reconstructs 2D representations, depicting the projected 3D features. At run-time we discard the decoder and only use our mapping layer to get $w \in W$ for additional guidance during template-matching.

this stage, templates and observations are matched based on their latent vector representation. We extend this part of the algorithm by introducing an additional network, we call GeoNet. The design is depicted in Figure 2. GeoNet follows the Encoder-Decoder design paradigm. We re-use the original encoder, mapping the RGB input (templates and observations) into the common latent space V . Given the latent vector, GeoNet predicts the key point projections within the original RGB input. We introduce a single additional layer to map vectors $v \in V$ to our input vector space W , and a separate head for our predicted features. To not interfere with the previously learned feature distribution in V , the original encoder is frozen during our decoder head training. For feature-matching we test two common methods of combining two signals, first summation, leading to a vector representation of $v + w$ and keeping the original vector dimensions of $1024 \times 16 \times 16$, as well as concatenating, giving us $v \oplus w$ and tensor shapes of $2048 \times 16 \times 16$. Both work fine with the GigaPoses cosine similarity metric used for matching. At inference, we can remove our decoder head and only use the mapping layer to generate $w \in W$. The decoder follows a conventional design and details can be found in Table 1.

Layer #	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18
Layer Type	CT2d	BN2d	SILU	D	CT2d	BN2d	SILU	D	CT2d	BN2d	SILU	D	CT2d	BN2d	SILU	D	Conv2d	Up
Output Shape	$512, 32^2$	$512, 32^2$	$512, 32^2$	$512, 32^2$	$256, 64^2$	$256, 64^2$	$256, 64^2$	$256, 64^2$	$128, 128^2$	$128, 128^2$	$128, 128^2$	$128, 128^2$	$64, 256^2$	$64, 256^2$	$64, 256^2$	$64, 256^2$	$1, 256^2$	$1, 224^2$
Param #	4,719,104	1,024	0	0	1,179,904	512	0	0	295,040	256	0	0	73,792	128	0	0	577	0

Table 1: Architecture of our GeoNet. CT2d stands for 2D transposed convolution, BN for batch normalization, D for dropout, and Up for upsampling.

For training, we use 943 meshes taken from the Google scanned objects dataset. We extract edge key points and project them into camera space, using the camera poses used for template generation. Next, we filter for visibility by asserting that the first intersection between object points and camera ray

is indeed the key point, and remove all occluded points. Finally, we project all visible key points to 2D image space. The resulting images are saved as binary images. Input RGB images are left unchanged from the original GigaPose: normalized, masked images of size 3x224x224. We use binary cross-entropy (BCE) loss.

Our training regime is as follows: We freeze the pre-trained encoder and only train our mapping layer, as well as our feature head. We split our 943 objects into 917 used for training, and 26 for validation. Training lasts for 15 epochs, using AdamW for optimization, learning rate of 0.001 and weight decay of 0.0005.

4 Results

We present quantitative and qualitative results. Our quantitative evaluation follows the methodology of the BOP Challenge: We compute the average of the three metrics, visible surface disparity (VSD), maximum symmetry-aware surface distance (MSSD) and maximum symmetry-aware projection distance (MSPD) [18, 42]. For illustration, we show samples from our validation and test sets, illustrating the geometric feature prediction provided by GeoNet.

4.1 Quantitative Results

Table 2: **Results on the 7 BOP core datasets.** Following the BOP challenge, we report Average Recall (AR) per dataset, as well as the per-method mean AR score. We also include the average run-time for each method. Our methods **GP-C** (concat) and **GP-A** (add) use the additional latent representations learned by GeoNet using edge key points. MP denotes MegaPose, 5H denotes 5 Hypotheses. Best per column performance highlighted in color.

Method	Detections	Refinement	LM-O	T-LESS	TUD-L	IC-BIN	ITODD	HB	YCB-V	Mean	Run-time
1 OSOP [38]	OSOP [38]	–	27.4	40.3	–	–	–	–	29.6	–	–
2 MP [20]	M-R-CNN [14]	–	18.7	19.7	20.5	15.3	8.00	18.6	13.9	16.2	–
3 ZS6D [1]	CNOS[28]	–	29.8	21.0	–	–	–	–	32.4	–	–
4 MP [20]	CNOS [28]	–	22.9	17.7	25.8	15.2	10.8	25.1	28.1	20.8	15.5 s
5 GP	CNOS [28]	–	29.6	26.4	30.0	22.3	17.5	34.1	27.8	26.8	0.4 s
6 GP-C	CNOS [28]	–	30.2	–	30.7	22.0	17.8	–	28.3	–	–
7 GP-A	CNOS [28]	–	30.2	27.2	30.7	22.2	17.8	34.2	28.2	27.2	0.4 s
8 MP [20]	CNOS [28]	MP [20]	49.9	47.7	65.3	36.7	31.5	65.4	60.1	50.9	17.0 s
9 GP	CNOS [28]	MP [20]	55.7	54.1	58.0	45.0	37.6	69.3	63.2	54.7	2.3 s
10 GP-C	CNOS [28]	MP [20]	56.2	–	58.9	45.3	38.7	–	64.5	–	–
11 GP-A	CNOS [28]	MP [20]	56.4	55.6	59.2	45.5	38.7	69.8	64.3	55.6	2.5 s
12 MP [20]	CNOS [28]	MP+5H [20]	56.0	50.7	68.4	41.4	33.8	70.4	62.1	54.7	21.9 s
13 GP	CNOS [28]	MP+5H [20]	59.8	56.5	63.1	47.3	39.7	72.2	66.1	57.8	7.7 s
14 GP-C	CNOS [28]	MP+5H [20]	60.6	–	65.4	47.8	39.8	–	66.0	–	–
15 GP-A	CNOS [28]	MP+5H [20]	60.4	57.6	64.8	48.2	39.8	69.8	66.6	58.2	9.8 s

We report OSOP, ZS6D, MegaPose, and the original GigaPose (GP) as baselines and compare 3 different settings: Results without refinement, results with

refinement using a single hypothesis, as well as using multiple hypotheses during refinement. The last tends to improve results further, at the cost of additional run-time. Our method outperforms the baselines on most of the core datasets. On LM-O, T-LESS, TUD-L, ITODD, and YCB-V we outperform GP in all three settings, with and without refinement. While GP performs better on IC-BIN without refinement, as soon as we add refinement we outperform with both, single and multiple hypotheses. On HB we outperform GP without refinement and with single hypothesis refinement, and only underperform in the 5 hypotheses case. YCB-V is the only dataset on which ZS6D outperforms MegaPose and all variants of GP. On YCB-V, our method comes in second place, outperforming the original GP in all three scenarios. In summary, our method increases the average across all datasets in all three scenarios.

Looking at run-time, our method adds only an insignificant cost when not using refinement (0.4 seconds vs. 0.4 seconds) and a little when using normal refinement (2.5 seconds vs. 2.3 seconds). Only when using 5 hypotheses, our run time is noticeably elevated (9.8 seconds vs 7.7 seconds).

4.2 Qualitative Results

Looking at the ground truth we generate from the 3D mesh and project into image space, we see that indeed, we find meaningful features. Our selection of key points cluster along geometric edges and ignore textural queues. Also, GeoNet is able to reproduce the key point location remarkably well. At test time, we show crops of unseen objects. Again, we find strong key point localization of GeoNet, indicating that indeed, the network has general understanding of the relevant features.

4.3 Discussion

We showed that incorporating a readily available geometric feature (edge key points) can increase the performance of template-based zero-shot pose estimation, supporting our hypothesis. Our evaluation emphasizes that the benefit of better initial pose estimates, as provided with our method, is relevant even when incorporation additional refinement steps. Future work can look into incorporating additional features.

5 Conclusion

In conclusion, our work presents a framework to extend the template-based pose estimator GigaPose by incorporating geometric features. The contributions of this work are threefold: Firstly, the paper proposes a framework to enhance GP by integrating additional geometric features into the pose estimation process. These features can be extracted from the available 3D meshes during the onboarding phase, providing valuable information for the template matching. Secondly, the paper suggests multiple relevant geometric features and provides

(a) Image triplets taken from our validation data, consisting of RGB, ground truth of projected key points, and key point predictions by GeoNet.

(b) Image tuples of the T-LESS test data, consisting of RGB crop and key point predictions in the given camera pose.

Fig. 3: Samples from our validation and test sets. We see good localization of relevant features in the extracted ground truth, and that our model is well able to predict them even on unseen objects, such as the T-Less dataset.

an explanation of how to extract them based on the object geometry. Thirdly, the paper selects one of the suggested geometric features and evaluates its performance on the core datasets of the BOP Challenge. The results demonstrate that the proposed approach outperforms the original GP algorithm, indicating that the incorporation of additional geometric features can significantly improve the relevant metrics without incurring much additional cost.

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References

1. Ausserlechner, P., Habegger, D., Thalhammer, S., Weibel, J.B., Vincze, M.: Zs6d: Zero-shot 6d object pose estimation using vision transformers. ArXiv **abs/2309.11986** (2023), <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:262084099>
2. Caron, M., Touvron, H., Misra, I., Jégou, H., Mairal, J., Bojanowski, P., Joulin, A.: Emerging properties in self-supervised vision transformers. 2021 IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV) pp. 9630–9640 (2021), <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:233444273>
3. Chang, A.X., Funkhouser, T.A., Guibas, L.J., Hanrahan, P., Huang, Q.X., Li, Z., Savarese, S., Savva, M., Song, S., Su, H., Xiao, J., Yi, L., Yu, F.: Shapenet: An information-rich 3d model repository. ArXiv **abs/1512.03012** (2015), <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:2554264>
4. Chen, J., Sun, M., Bao, T., Zhao, R., Wu, L., He, Z.: Zeropose: Cad-model-based zero-shot pose estimation (2023), <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:258960481>
5. Cohen-Steiner, D., Morvan, J.M.: Restricted delaunay triangulations and normal cycle. In: SCG '03 (2003), <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:5777927>
6. Deng, X., Geng, J., Bretl, T., Xiang, Y., Fox, D.: icaps: Iterative category-level object pose and shape estimation. IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters **PP**, 1–1 (2021), <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:245650812>
7. Di, Y., Manhardt, F., Wang, G., Ji, X., Navab, N., Tombari, F.: So-pose: Exploiting self-occlusion for direct 6d pose estimation. 2021 IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV) pp. 12376–12385 (2021), <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:237213284>
8. Dosovitskiy, A., Beyer, L., Kolesnikov, A., Weissenborn, D., Zhai, X., Unterthiner, T., Dehghani, M., Minderer, M., Heigold, G., Gelly, S., Uszkoreit, J., Houlsby, N.: An image is worth 16x16 words: Transformers for image recognition at scale. ArXiv **abs/2010.11929** (2020), <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:225039882>
9. Downs, L., Francis, A., Koenig, N., Kinman, B., Hickman, R.M., Reymann, K., McHugh, T.B., Vanhoucke, V.: Google scanned objects: A high-quality dataset of 3d scanned household items. 2022 International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA) pp. 2553–2560 (2022), <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:248392390>
10. Fan, Z., Pan, P., Wang, P., Jiang, Y., Xu, D., Jiang, H., Wang, Z.: Pope: 6-dof promptable pose estimation of any object, in any scene, with one reference. ArXiv **abs/2305.15727** (2023), <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:258887814>
11. Fischler, M.A., Bolles, R.C.: Random sample consensus: a paradigm for model fitting with applications to image analysis and automated cartography. Commun. ACM **24**, 381–395 (1981), <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:972888>
12. Girdhar, R., El-Nouby, A., Liu, Z., Singh, M., Alwala, K.V., Joulin, A., Misra, I.: Imagebind one embedding space to bind them all. 2023 IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR) pp. 15180–15190 (2023), <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:258564264>

13. Harris, C., Stephens, M., et al.: A combined corner and edge detector. In: Alvey vision conference. vol. 15, pp. 10–5244. Citeseer (1988)
14. He, K., Gkioxari, G., Dollár, P., Girshick, R.B.: Mask r-cnn (2017), <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:54465873>
15. He, X., Sun, J., Wang, Y., Huang, D., Bao, H., Zhou, X.: Onepose++: Keypoint-free one-shot object pose estimation without CAD models. In: Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems (2022)
16. He, Y., Wang, Y., Fan, H., Sun, J., Chen, Q.: Fs6d: Few-shot 6d pose estimation of novel objects. 2022 IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR) pp. 6804–6814 (2022), <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:247763100>
17. Hodan, T., Baráth, D., Matas, J.: Epos: Estimating 6d pose of objects with symmetries. 2020 IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR) pp. 11700–11709 (2020), <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:214743136>
18. Hodan, T., Sundermeyer, M., Labbe, Y., Nguyen, V.N., Wang, G., Brachmann, E., Drost, B., Lepetit, V., Rother, C., Matas, J.: Bop challenge 2023 on detection, segmentation and pose estimation of seen and unseen rigid objects. arXiv preprint arXiv:2403.09799 (2024)
19. Kirillov, A., Mintun, E., Ravi, N., Mao, H., Rolland, C., Gustafson, L., Xiao, T., Whitehead, S., Berg, A.C., Lo, W.Y., Dollár, P., Girshick, R.B.: Segment anything. 2023 IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV) pp. 3992–4003 (2023), <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:257952310>
20. Labb'e, Y., Manuelli, L., Mousavian, A., Tyree, S., Birchfield, S., Tremblay, J., Carpentier, J., Aubry, M., Fox, D., Sivic, J.: Megapose: 6d pose estimation of novel objects via render & compare. In: Conference on Robot Learning (2022), <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:254636085>
21. Lin, J., Wei, Z., Li, Z., Xu, S., Jia, K., Li, Y.: Dualposenet: Category-level 6d object pose and size estimation using dual pose network with refined learning of pose consistency. 2021 IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV) pp. 3540–3549 (2021), <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:232185618>
22. Lin, Y.C., Florence, P.R., Barron, J.T., Rodriguez, A., Isola, P., Lin, T.Y.: inerf: Inverting neural radiance fields for pose estimation. 2021 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS) pp. 1323–1330 (2020), <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:228083990>
23. Liu, X., Zhang, R., Zhang, C., Fu, B., Tang, J., Liang, X., Tang, J., Cheng, X., Zhang, Y., Wang, G., Ji, X.: Gdrnpp (2022), https://github.com/shanice-1/gdrnpp_bop2022
24. Liu, Y., Wen, Y., Peng, S., Lin, C.H., Long, X., Komura, T., Wang, W.: Gen6d: Generalizable model-free 6-dof object pose estimation from rgb images. In: European Conference on Computer Vision (2022), <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:248366253>
25. Luo, G., Dunlap, L., Park, D.H., Holynski, A., Darrell, T.: Diffusion hyperfeatures: Searching through time and space for semantic correspondence. In: Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems (2023)
26. Moreno-Noguer, F., Lepetit, V., Fua, P.V.: Accurate non-iterative $o(n)$ solution to the pnp problem. 2007 IEEE 11th International Conference on Computer Vision pp. 1–8 (2007), <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:3107373>
27. Nguyen, V.N., Groueix, T., Salzmann, M., Lepetit, V.: Gigapose: Fast and robust novel object pose estimation via one correspondence. ArXiv [abs/2311.14155](https://arxiv.org/abs/2311.14155) (2023), <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:265445006>

28. Nguyen, V.N., Hodan, T., Ponimatkin, G., Groueix, T., Lepetit, V.: Cnos: A strong baseline for cad-based novel object segmentation. 2023 IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision Workshops (ICCVW) pp. 2126–2132 (2023), <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:259991698>
29. Oquab, M., Darcet, T., Moutakanni, T., Vo, H.Q., Szafraniec, M., Khalidov, V., Fernandez, P., Haziza, D., Massa, F., El-Nouby, A., Assran, M., Ballas, N., Galuba, W., Howes, R., Huang, P.Y.B., Li, S.W., Misra, I., Rabbat, M.G., Sharma, V., Synnaeve, G., Xu, H., Jégou, H., Mairal, J., Labatut, P., Joulin, A., Bojanowski, P.: DINOv2: Learning robust visual features without supervision. ArXiv **abs/2304.07193** (2023), <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:258170077>
30. Örnek, E.P., Labb'e, Y., Tekin, B., Ma, L., Keskin, C., Forster, C., Hodan, T.: Foundpose: Unseen object pose estimation with foundation features. ArXiv **abs/2311.18809** (2023), <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:265506592>
31. Pan, P., Fan, Z., Feng, B.Y., Wang, P., Li, C., Wang, Z.: Learning to estimate 6dof pose from limited data: A few-shot, generalizable approach using rgb images. ArXiv **abs/2306.07598** (2023), <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:259144908>
32. Peng, S., Liu, Y., Huang, Q.X., Bao, H., Zhou, X.: Pvnnet: Pixel-wise voting network for 6dof pose estimation. 2019 IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR) pp. 4556–4565 (2018), <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:57189382>
33. Pitteri, G., Ilic, S., Lepetit, V.: Cornet: Generic 3d corners for 6d pose estimation of new objects without retraining. 2019 IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision Workshop (ICCVW) pp. 2807–2815 (2019), <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:201698155>
34. Ranftl, R., Bochkovskiy, A., Koltun, V.: Vision transformers for dense prediction. 2021 IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV) pp. 12159–12168 (2021), <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:232352612>
35. Ranftl, R., Lasinger, K., Hafner, D., Schindler, K., Koltun, V.: Towards robust monocular depth estimation: Mixing datasets for zero-shot cross-dataset transfer. IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence **44**(3) (2022)
36. Reis, D., Kupec, J., Hong, J., Daoudi, A.: Real-time flying object detection with yolov8. ArXiv **abs/2305.09972** (2023), <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:258741093>
37. Rombach, R., Blattmann, A., Lorenz, D., Esser, P., Ommer, B.: High-resolution image synthesis with latent diffusion models. In: 2022 IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR). pp. 10674–10685 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1109/CVPR52688.2022.01042>
38. Shugurov, I.S., Li, F., Busam, B., Ilic, S.: Osop: A multi-stage one shot object pose estimation framework. 2022 IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR) pp. 6825–6834 (2022), <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:247779245>
39. Sipiran, I., Bustos, B.: Harris 3d: a robust extension of the harris operator for interest point detection on 3d meshes. The Visual Computer **27**, 963–976 (2011), <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:15897631>
40. Song, C., Song, J., Huang, Q.X.: Hybridpose: 6d object pose estimation under hybrid representations. 2020 IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR) pp. 428–437 (2020), <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:210023370>

41. Sun, J., Shen, Z., Wang, Y., Bao, H., Zhou, X.: Loftr: Detector-free local feature matching with transformers. 2021 IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR) pp. 8918–8927 (2021), <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:232478646>
42. Sundermeyer, M., Hodaň, T., Labbe, Y., Wang, G., Brachmann, E., Drost, B., Rother, C., Matas, J.: Bop challenge 2022 on detection, segmentation and pose estimation of specific rigid objects. In: Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition. pp. 2784–2793 (2023)
43. Tang, L., Jia, M., Wang, Q., Phoo, C.P., Hariharan, B.: Emergent correspondence from image diffusion. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems* **36**, 1363–1389 (2023)
44. Umeyama, S.: Least-squares estimation of transformation parameters between two point patterns. *IEEE Trans. Pattern Anal. Mach. Intell.* **13**, 376–380 (1991), <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:206421766>
45. Wang, G., Manhardt, F., Tombari, F., Ji, X.: Gdr-net: Geometry-guided direct regression network for monocular 6d object pose estimation. 2021 IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR) pp. 16606–16616 (2021), <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:232035418>
46. Wang, H., Sridhar, S., Huang, J., Valentin, J.P.C., Song, S., Guibas, L.J.: Normalized object coordinate space for category-level 6d object pose and size estimation. 2019 IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR) pp. 2637–2646 (2019), <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:57761160>
47. Wen, B., Yang, W., Kautz, J., Birchfield, S.T.: Foundationpose: Unified 6d pose estimation and tracking of novel objects. *ArXiv abs/2312.08344* (2023), <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:266191252>
48. Wen, Y., Li, X., Pan, H., Yang, L., Wang, Z., Komura, T., Wang, W.: Disp6d: Disentangled implicit shape and pose learning for scalable 6d pose estimation. In: Avidan, S., Brostow, G., Cissé, M., Farinella, G.M., Hassner, T. (eds.) *Computer Vision – ECCV 2022*. pp. 404–421. Springer Nature Switzerland, Cham (2022)
49. Yang, L., Kang, B., Huang, Z., Xu, X., Feng, J., Zhao, H.: Depth anything: Unleashing the power of large-scale unlabeled data. *ArXiv abs/2401.10891* (2024), <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:267061016>
50. Yang, L., Kang, B., Huang, Z., Xu, X., Feng, J., Zhao, H.: Depth anything: Unleashing the power of large-scale unlabeled data. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2401.10891* (2024)
51. Zhan, G., Zheng, C., Xie, W., Zisserman, A.: What does stable diffusion know about the 3d scene? *ArXiv abs/2310.06836* (2023), <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:263829471>
52. Zhang, J., Herrmann, C., Hur, J., Cabrera, L.P., Jampani, V., Sun, D., Yang, M.H.: A tale of two features: Stable diffusion complements dino for zero-shot semantic correspondence (2023)
53. Zhang, J., Herrmann, C., Hur, J., Chen, E., Jampani, V., Sun, D., Yang, M.H.: Telling left from right: Identifying geometry-aware semantic correspondence (2023)
54. Zhao, X., Ding, W.Y., An, Y., Du, Y., Yu, T., Li, M., Tang, M., Wang, J.: Fast segment anything. *ArXiv abs/2306.12156* (2023), <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:259212104>